

Microcanonical Partition Function for Particles using the Physical Π and the reduced Physical Π

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Abstract

Three different partition functions are well-known and described in statistical physics. Here, the microcanonical partition function for the description of intra-particle interactions and with it for the masses of the particles is presented. In statistical physics three different partition functions are known. These are the microcanonical, the canonical and the macro-canonical partition functions. Thereby due to the properties of quantum mechanics and superposition the partition function described here is of the nature of the microcanonical partition function. The masses and energies of the particles result from the microcanonical partition function. The energy of an elementary particle is proportional to the mass on one hand and to the microcanonical partition function on the other. The constant of proportionality also called the density with respect to the microcanonical partition function is found experimentally to be identical with Rydberg's constant. Rydberg energy is found to be the microcanonical density operator for this ensemble. The relationships found for the proton, the electron and the sigma particle are then generalized for all particles.

Introduction

Color Force and Strong Interaction

The color force is defined as a fundamental property of quarks, characterized by the associations of quarks within baryons [1]. The strong interaction extends beyond neutrons and protons, resulting in extraordinary properties not previously noted between nucleons. The baryons facilitate the strong interaction and a residual force that does not taper off with distance in the well-known way. Furthermore this process effectively results in the confinement of quarks. Conventionally, naturally occurring energy emerges leading to quark-antiquark pair production under certain conditions [2,3,4]. Due to the strong nature of the color force carried by the exchange of gluons, the quarks do not undergo separation.

Previous studies report that within the confinement within a given space, the quarks behave as free particles, as the color force exerts minimum pressure at short distances [5]. Stronger forces begin to be realized as further separation occurs. This concept is analogous to the widely held scientific understanding that ordinary mesons composed of conventional quarks and anti-quarks are bound closely by the color force. This construct has immense scientific importance, especially in providing an in-depth understanding of atomic nuclei and defining the associations and interactions between neutrons and protons [5,6,7]. The mediation of these relationships by gluons forms the foundation of quantum chromodynamics (QCD) and is commonly used to discuss complex physical phenomena, including chiral symmetry breaking, asymptotic freedom, and hadron confinement [8, 9].

Gluons act as gauge bosons and/or as exchange particles that facilitate interaction between quarks via the strong force. Essentially, they enable the exchange of photons between charged particles via the electromagnetic force in addition to binding them together to form hadrons. Bosons are carrier particles with full-integer spin numbers, while fermions have odd half-integer spin numbers. Both types of particles act as force carriers, with the latter obeying the Pauli exclusion principle [8,9,10]. Conventionally, the color charge depends on the configuration of the particles. For

instance, when mixed together, “red”, “blue”, and “green” will result in white, with a color net charge of zero. Additionally, the color force can act in a different way, resulting in the emergence of “cyan”, “magenta”, and “yellow”, the three anti-colors. They also form a net color charge of zero. Binding can be accomplished either by color – anticolor interaction as in the mesons and/or by three color interactions as realized in the neutron and/or within the proton.

Fundamentally, the color charges exhibit a force that tends to remain enhance despite separation resulting in a corresponding increase in energy and subsequent spontaneous production of a quark–antiquark pair if separation is large enough [11].

Further important interactions on the particle level are the 3-gluon vertex and the 4-gluon vertex interaction. Both of them are pure gluon- gluon interactions. So we have four fundamental interactions on the particle level: the color / anti-color, the color, the 3-gluon vertex, and the 4-gluon vertex.

The concept of the color force has been introduced by Oscar Greenberg, who first theorized the existence of quarks in 1964 [12]. This theoretical physicist documented the phenomenon after an extensive analysis of the Pauli Exclusion Principle and its relation to the construct. Greenberg believed that his theory explained the coexistence of quarks within select hadrons despite exhibiting identical quantum states [13], a situation that would otherwise have constituted a theoretical impossibility due to its violation of the Pauli exclusion principle [14,15,16].

Greenberg proposed in 1964 that quarks were (para-) fermions of order 3, the corresponding implicit degree of freedom was soon perceived by Han and Nambu and called color [13].

Since that time, there have been extensive developments in quantum chromodynamics (QCD) toward an improved understanding of quarks and the theory of the color force. Other notable personalities have made immense contributions, including Murray Gell-Mann, Heinrich Leutwyler, and Harald Fritsch. The concept has been revolutionary in enhancing the understanding of quantum electrodynamics (QED) due to the many similarities between the two fields (QCD and QED). The strong force has been determined to have minimal behavioral autonomy over the basic subatomic particles constituting atomic nuclei.

The theories of the strong force and other associated aspects of quantum chromodynamics (QCD) were developed to provide an improved understanding of the roles of each aspect of the three-value color charge. Fundamental QCD concepts, including gluons, antiquarks, and quarks, remained relatively obscure prior to the discovery of the color force.

Starting from the well-known connection between the Rydberg constant and the electron mass, we here start with:

$$E_{Rydberg} = \frac{1}{2} m_e c^2 \alpha^2 \quad (1)$$

where alpha is the well-known Sommerfeld fine structure constant.

Now, there are several methods and formulas for calculating the Sommerfeld fine structure constant, which is equal to approximately 1/137, by using the mathematical constant pi.

We use the following formula for the Sommerfeld fine structure constant alpha:

$$\alpha = \frac{2 \cdot \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{3\pi}\right)}}}}}{27\pi^2} \quad (2)$$

Thereby pi might be determined experimentally. It is a value near by the mathematical pi but is not necessary identically with the mathematical pi (physical pi here is 3.141677).

Next, we calculate the smallest quantum of mass and/or energy according to the Rydberg energy:

$$E_{Rydberg} = \frac{1}{2} m_e c^2 \alpha^2 \quad (1)$$

in [eV], this gets

$$E_{Rydberg} = 13.60569 \text{ eV} \quad (3)$$

$$m_{Rydberg} = 13.60569 \text{ eV}/c^2 \quad (4)$$

This number is postulated here to be the smallest possible amount of mass and/or energy involved in crystallization of energy towards mass and in mass formation. It is the smallest amount of binding energy.

From both equations above, we obtain a formula for the electron mass, as follows:

$$m_e = \frac{1}{2} 3^2 (3\pi)^4 \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{3\pi}\right)}}}}} \right)^4 m_{Ryd} \quad \text{or} \quad E_e = \frac{1}{2} 3^2 (3\pi)^4 \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{3\pi}\right)}}}}} \right)^4 E_{Ryd} \quad (5)$$

A special case of the microcanonical density, in general, is defined as:

$$\rho_{E0} = \frac{1}{Z_m} \sum_{n=1}^{dimH} |E_0, n\rangle \quad (6)$$

a special case of this here is:

$$E_e = Z_{m,e} \cdot \rho = Z_{m,e} \cdot E_{Ryd} \quad (7)$$

With E_e as Energy of the electron, $Z_{m,e}$ as microcanonical partition function, E_{Ryd} Rydberg energy, ρ (roh) as microcanonical density operator

We now consider the equation (5) to be a special case. We get the following generalization of this formula (5). We do so to get the following generalized equation.

$$m_{particle} = 2^a 3^b (3\pi)^c \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[8]{\left(1 - \frac{1}{3\pi}\right)}} \right)^d m_{Ryd}, \quad (8)$$

with a=-1, b=2, c=4, and d=4 for the electron e

We now postulate that we can obtain all other particle masses through different combinations of (a,b,c,d)-tuples. But the question keeps how to interpret this last equation. Thereby the electron is thought to be composed of rishons (smaller entities) as we will see later. The (a,b,c,d)-tuple is thought to describe bindings between the rishons in an electron as we will see later.

The Feynman-like ensemble of binding states within a single particle is related to the particle's microcanonical partition function

A single particle is thought to be formulated as a series of different binding states (a,b,c,d). Every of these series of different binding states forms an ensemble comparable to a statistical microcanonical ensemble as known from statistical thermodynamics and quantum mechanics.

We here deal with quantum mechanical super-positions of Feynman diagrams. The occupations that occur here are thought to be super-positions of Feynman diagrams. These super-positions have no statistical distribution, fluctuation and/or standard deviation. Each Feynman diagram is thought to be equally weighted. The quantum mechanical overlays are always present immediately. There is no "distribution" of these microcanonical states. Every microcanonical state is equally important, equally distributed and equally weighted.

In statistical quantum mechanics, if a system can be subdivided into N subsystems, then the total microcanonical partition function is given by the sum of the different constellations and/or by the product of the partial microcanonical partition functions for the individual subsystems. Z and/or Omega is representing the **microcanonical partition function**, which in turn is depending on the multiplicity, and/or number of possible configurations of the system and/or the specific particle [17].

$$Z_m = \int d\tau \cdot \delta(E_0 - H) = \prod_{j=1}^N \zeta_j \quad \text{or} \quad \Omega_m = \int d\tau \cdot \delta(E_0 - H) = \prod_{j=1}^N \omega_j \quad (9a+9b)$$

Accordingly, the probability P follows [17] in the following way:

$$P = \frac{1}{\Omega_m} = \frac{1}{\prod_{j=1}^N \omega_j} \quad (10)$$

Starting from a Feynman-like ensemble for a complex particle, each and every single binding form or configuration is regarded as such a statistical subsystem here. In general there are four major binding forms to consider here: the two-quark binding (color and anticolor), the three-quark binding (three colors), the 3-vertex gluon interaction, and the 4-vertex gluon interaction.

Within each of these binding-type forms, all the remaining sub-subseries elements represent different subforms of the corresponding binding- type. The elements of these subforms all have the same physical properties. Thus, their microcanonical partition function, in turn, has the form of a power-function:

Microcanonical power function:

$$\zeta_j = \zeta_{jj}^n \quad \text{or} \quad \omega_j = \omega_{jj}^n \quad (11a+11b)$$

Here, n is the number of sub-series present in the particle, meaning the number of two-quark interactions, three-quark interactions, 3-vertex gluon interactions, or 4-vertex gluon interactions. ζ_{jj} is the type of binding and thereby representing the basic energy for each of the basal binding states, i.e., the basal energy of the two-quark binding state, the three quark binding state, the 3-vertex state, and/or the 4-vertex state.

The basal energy ζ_{jj} of each individual binding state can be visualized by an arrow in a Feynman-like diagram and corresponds to a single gluon. The basal energy of the two-quark binding is represented by two arrows leading us to two gluons, one colorless and one colored. This is leading us to a basis of 2 for this type of interaction. The basal energy of three-quark binding is represented by three arrows leading us to three gluons (r, g, and b). This in turn leads us to a basis of 3 for this type of interaction. The basal energy of a 3-vertex gluon interaction can be visualized by three half-circles (the Dyson-Schwinger equations leading to the swordfish diagram) and this leading us to an arrow of the length of 3π . So the basis of this interaction is 3π . The basal energy of a 4-vertex gluon interaction is given

by $\frac{1}{\sqrt[8]{1 - \frac{1}{3\pi}}}$ as we will see later on.

Dyson-Schwinger equations, also named Schwinger-Dyson equations, are relations between various Green's functions in the quantum field theory as formulated by Freeman Dyson and Julian S. Schwinger. Since they represent the equations of motion for the Green's functions, they are also often called the Euler-Lagrange equations of a quantum field theory. There are infinitely many functional differential equations, all of which are directly or indirectly coupled to one another. That is why one often speaks of the infinite tower of the Dyson-Schwinger equations.

The Dyson equations were originally derived by Dyson by summing up an infinite number of Feynman diagrams and were extended by Schwinger in his quantum action principle to all Green's functions of the quantum field theory. Graphically in Feynman diagrams sword fish diagrams result if Dyson-Schwinger equations are applied to describe the 3 gluon vertices, as virtual particles. Summing-up these three half circles and overlaying the way-length within the 3 gluon vertex we get a way-length of 3π in length. If we associate the way-length of a virtual particle with its energy, then the energy needed for the 3 gluon vertex is 3π the amount of a "normal interaction".

The basis of this interaction gets 3π .

In the following considerations we will present microcanonical partition functions in the context of particles at the elementary level. These particles consist either of rishons, of quarks and gluons or of gluon alone.

Both quarks and leptons are thought to consist of even smaller particles the so called rishons. There are two fundamental rishons: the T-rishon and the V-rishon. All this is in-line with the H. Harari preon model described e.g. in “A schematic model of quarks and leptons” Physics Letters 1997 [18].

An important initial hypothesis is that these particles cannot be broken down into even smaller particles.

And another important hypothesis is that the fundamental particles (as V and T) do not possess any energy and/or mass. All energy and/or mass is the result from intra-particular interactions.

From these basic assumptions it follows that even leptons like the electron need to be composed particles and that there needs to be some sort of interaction inside leptons like the electron.

The total partition function of a particle can be seen as an ensemble of subsystems and can be expressed as a product of the individual microcanonical partition functions for these subsystems:

$$Z_m = \prod_{j=1}^N \zeta_j = \prod_{j=1}^N \zeta_{jj}^n = \zeta_2 \cdot \dots \cdot \zeta_3 \cdot \dots \cdot \zeta_{3\text{-vertex}} \cdot \dots \cdot \zeta_{4\text{-vertex}} \cdot \dots = \zeta_{2j}^a \cdot \zeta_{3j}^b \cdot \zeta_{3\text{-vertex},j}^c \cdot \zeta_{4\text{-vertex},j}^d \quad (12)$$

$$\Omega_m = \prod_{j=1}^N \omega_j = \prod_{j=1}^N \omega_{jj}^n = \omega_2 \cdot \dots \cdot \omega_3 \cdot \dots \cdot \omega_{3\text{-vertex}} \cdot \dots \cdot \omega_{4\text{-vertex}} = \omega_{2j}^a \cdot \omega_{3j}^b \cdot \omega_{3\text{-vertex},j}^c \cdot \omega_{4\text{-vertex},j}^d \quad (13)$$

Consequently, at the elementary level, the microcanonical partition function must result from a product of individual partial partition functions.

Considering the quark color interactions

The task of these individual partial microcanonical partition functions is to describe the individual interactions in a particle and capture them mathematically. The following question therefore arises: What interactions exist at the elementary level? The answer is: the color interactions among three quarks (i.e., **rgb** and **rgb**). In interactions of this form, three quarks and three standard gluons are always involved simultaneously. The number of standard gluons or interactions is thus three to the power of n. The partial microcanonical partition function for this kind of interaction is consequently three to the power of b, where b is the number of three-gluon interactions that exist per particle.

$$\zeta_3 = \omega_3 = 3^b \quad \text{for } n=b \text{ three-color interactions per particle} \quad (14)$$

Another elementary interaction is the color-anticolor interaction between two quarks (e.g., in $q\bar{q}$). Two quarks (a colored quark and an anticolored quark) and two standard gluons (a neutral and a colored gluon) are always involved in this interaction. The number of gluons or interactions is therefore two to the power of a. The corresponding partial microcanonical partition function is similarly two to the power of a.

Here, a denotes the number of two-gluon interactions per particle. For quantum mechanical reasons, this bond is always mediated by two gluons that are exchanged between the quarks one after the other: first, a neutral gluon is exchanged, and then, a color gluon is exchanged.

$$\zeta_2 = \omega_2 = 2^a \quad \text{for } n=a \text{ color-anticolor interactions per particle} \quad (15)$$

Considering the gluon vertices

According to the Dyson–Schwinger equation (DSE), the **3-vertex** interaction of a gluon can be described as the sum of three semicircles.

The 3-gluon vertex can be converted into a circular structure using a DSE on-loop correction. Doing so creates three circles with an entrance and with a 3-vertex, all facing each other at 180° [19]. This corresponds to a path length between entry and 3-vertex of 3 times 1π . When using the Dyson–Schwinger equations, three such swordfish- diagrams arise, each of it with a weighting of $\frac{1}{2}$, so that the loop correction leads to a total path length of 3π for the 3-gluon vertex [19], [20].

$$\zeta_{3\text{-vertex},j} = \omega_{3\text{-vertex},j} = \frac{1}{2}(2\pi) + \frac{1}{2}(2\pi) + \frac{1}{2}(2\pi) = 3\pi \quad (16)$$

The distance that a gluon travels in this form of interaction is thus 3π times as long as the ordinary gluon distance in one of the two interactions mentioned above. Consequently, the partial microcanonical partition function for this form of interaction can be described as the term 3π to the power of c . Here, c is again the number of interactions of this type per particle.

$$\zeta_{3\text{-vertex}} = \omega_{3\text{-vertex}} = (3\pi)^c \quad \text{for } n=c \text{ 3-vertex interactions per particle} \quad (17)$$

Now, the **4-vertex** interaction between two gluons is considered. The probability of this interaction occurring is proportional to the total probability (100%) minus the probability of the 3-vertex interaction occurring. This probability of the 3-vertex interaction occurring is the reciprocal of the microcanonical partition function of the 3-vertex interaction. Therefore, the probability of the 4-vertex interaction occurring is proportional to $1-1/(3\pi)$. Since this interaction corresponds to a collision event involving two of the eight possible gluons, the 8th root of the term $1-1/(3\pi)$ must be taken. The partial microcanonical partition function of the 4-vertex interaction is then the reciprocal of this probability and thus proportional to $1/(\text{8th root}(1-1/(3\pi)))$ to the power of d . Again, d denotes the number of interactions of this type per particle. This is leading us to the following equation:

$$\zeta_{4\text{-vertex}} = \omega_{4\text{-vertex}} = \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[8]{1 - \frac{1}{3\pi}}} \right)^d \quad \text{for } n=d \text{ 4-vertex interactions per particle} \quad (18)$$

A closer look at the quark color interactions a and b: Binding and Nonbinding events

When looking at the partial microcanonical partition functions ζ_2 and ζ_3 , we need to differentiate between events that have a binding nature, which should be considered to lead to negative energy (release of energy), and events that have a nonbinding nature, which lead to positive energy (consumption of energy). This leads us to quotients for ζ_2 and ζ_3 , which are defined as follows:

$$\zeta_2 = \omega_2 = \frac{2^{a(\text{nonbinding})}}{2^{a(\text{binding})}} \quad \text{meaning that } a > 0 \Rightarrow \text{nonbinding event} \Rightarrow \text{energy needed} \quad (19)$$

$$a < 0 \Rightarrow \text{binding event} \Rightarrow \text{energy released}$$

$$\zeta_3 = \omega_3 = \frac{3^{b(\text{nonbinding})}}{3^{b(\text{binding})}} \quad \text{meaning that } b > 0 \Rightarrow \text{nonbinding event} \Rightarrow \text{energy needed} \quad (20)$$

$$b < 0 \Rightarrow \text{binding event} \Rightarrow \text{energy released}$$

Calculation of all possible combinations of interaction possibilities for the nucleon (proton or neutron)

To calculate the number of interaction possibilities for the proton, a hypothesis must first be formulated:

In the following, the hypothesis is formulated that in the ground state, only two gluon–gluon interactions can subsequently follow one another. More than two interactions can follow one another only in higher or excited energy states of the nucleon. Such higher excitation states are realized in the sigma baryon, for example.

Based on this premise, the number of possible interaction combinations can be counted graphically as illustrated in figure 1. The following numbers of possible combinations result for a nucleon in the ground state:

The total microcanonical partition function for the nucleon ((a,b,c,d)=(0,-2,9,4)) is as follows:

$$Z_{m,p} = \Omega_p = 2^0 \cdot 3^{-2} \cdot (3\pi)^9 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[8]{1 - \frac{1}{3\pi}}} \right)^4 = 6.8953127 \cdot 10^7 \quad (21)$$

The total microcanonical partition function for the neutral pion ((a,b,c,d)=(-1,1,7,0)) is as follows:

$$Z_{m,pion} = \Omega_{pion} = 2^{-1} \cdot 3^1 \cdot (3\pi)^7 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[8]{1 - \frac{1}{3\pi}}} \right)^0 = 9.908071 \cdot 10^6 \quad (22)$$

The total microcanonical partition function for the neutral sigma baryon ((a,b,c,d)=(-3,2,8,16)) is as follows:

$$Z_{m,Sigma} = \Omega_{Sigma} = 2^{-3} \cdot 3^2 \cdot (3\pi)^8 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[8]{1 - \frac{1}{3\pi}}} \right)^{16} = 8.7648980 \cdot 10^7 \quad (23)$$

For the electron, the following total microcanonical partition function Z_e is obtained:

$$Z_{m,e} = \Omega_e = 2^{-1} \cdot 3^2 \cdot (3\pi)^4 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[8]{1 - \frac{1}{3\pi}}} \right)^4 = 37553 \quad (24)$$

At a first sight the electron seems to have nothing to do with gluon interactions. However,- according to the rishons-model (or pre-on model, or so called Harari model) also the leptons as the electrons are composed from even smaller particles, the Rishons. According to Harari these are the T- and V-particles. The rishons- composition of the electron is anti-T; anti-T; anti-T. So it is composed from three identical anti-T particles. In a later variant Harari and Seiberg have differentiated the electron to be composed from anti-T-R, anti-T-R, and anti-T-L [21]. They talk about the electron being an $e^- = (T_R T_R) T_L$ particle (table 8, page 156 in [21]).

The electrons n-tupel (-1;2;4;4) can now be interpreted as follows: the electron inside itself has 1 binding 2-particle interaction (the so called binding hypercolor H according to Harari et al, e.g. anti-T-R and anti-T-R), 2-non binding 3-particle interactions (anti-T-R; anti-T-R; anti-T-L and anti-T-L; anti-T-R; anti-T-R), four 3-vertex interactions and four 4-vertex interactions. In case of the electron these four 3-vertex and four 4-vertex interactions might be substantially different from the 3 and 4 gluon-vertices in case of the more complex particles. Most likely in case of the electron these both interactions (3-vertex and 4-vertex) are combined to each other and form four combined (3-vertex/4-vertex)- interactions. The easiest way to realize this structure is a linear formation. In this linear formation we start with the first anti-T, followed the first 3-vertex, next two 4-vertices, a second 3-vertex, the second anti-t, the third 3-vertex, two more 4-vertices, the fourth 3-vertex and the last anti-T-L. Counted all together we used the (-1;2;4;4) elements to form the structure of the electron.

Elements of the Higher Lepton Generations

Elbaz et al expanded the Harari Preon model towards higher generation of leptons [22], [23], [24]. To do so they interpreted the higher lepton generations as excited states of the electron.

If we look at the exponent tuples for the muon (-3;2;7;3) and the tauon (1;2;7;7) we see a further analogy. Also in the present theory they are both excited states with an increased number of intra-particle interactions. We here now described the interactions, which make the excited states of the leptons and quarks, for which Elbaz and others were looking for.

It can be realized that by comparing complex particles and leptons, even if different in nature, there seems to be some kind of repetition of the fundamental rules and laws between leptons and the more complex particles. Analogously the interactions and vertices seem to be some kind repeated.

Weak and Strong Interaction

If we associate the n-tuple of compound particles (as baryons and mesons) with their strong interaction (color interaction) and the n-tuple of leptons and quarks with their weak interaction we easily can see, that there are a lot of analogy between strong and weak interaction. Both types of interaction can be divided into 4 more basal interactions (which are the 2-particle, 3-particle, 3-vertex and the 4-vertex interactions).

However there are also some differences between the strong and the weak interaction. First of all we do not see negative a and/or b-exponents within the weak interaction for quarks but only for leptons.

However if we transfer this to the beta decay, which is in most cases the decay of a neutron, we get.

We can also have a closer look at typical weak interactions as the beta-decay for example:

Beta-Decay

$$d^{-0.3} \rightarrow u^{+0.67} + W^- \rightarrow u^{+0.67} + e^- + \bar{\nu} \quad (25)$$

in the rishon model:

$$\underline{VVT}^{-0.3} \rightarrow \underline{TTV}^{+0.67} + \underline{(TT)TVV(V)} \rightarrow \underline{TTV}^{+0.67} + \underline{TTT} + \underline{VVV}$$

In the interaction-model (n-tupel model):

$$\underline{(2;2;4;8)} \rightarrow (1;2;4;8) + \underline{(0;0;10;5)} \rightarrow (1;2;4;8) + \underline{(-1;2;4;4)} + \underline{(-1;-2;0;0)}$$

Myon-Decay

$$\mu^- \rightarrow W^- + \nu_\mu \rightarrow e^- + \underline{\nu_e} + \nu_\mu \quad (26)$$

Rishon:

$$[\underline{\text{TTT}} + 3\underline{\text{VV}}] \rightarrow \underline{(\text{TT})\text{TVV}(\text{V})^-} + \text{VVV} \rightarrow \underline{\text{TTT}} + \underline{\text{VVV}} + \text{VVV}$$

Interactions:

$$\underline{(-3;2;7;3)} \rightarrow \underline{(0;0;10;5)} + (-1;-0;0;0) \rightarrow \underline{(-1;2;4;4)} + \underline{(-1;-2;0;0)} + (-1;-0;0;0)$$

Pion-Decay

$$\pi^-(\underline{\mathbf{u}}, \mathbf{d}) \rightarrow W^- \rightarrow \mu^- + \underline{\nu_\mu} \quad (27)$$

Rishon:

$$\underline{\text{TTV}}^{-0.67} + \underline{\text{VVT}}^{-0.3} \rightarrow \underline{(\text{TT})\text{TVV}(\text{V})^-} \rightarrow \underline{\text{TTT}} + \underline{\text{VVV}}$$

Interactions:

$$\underline{(1;2;4;8)} + \underline{(2;2;4;8)} \rightarrow \underline{(0;0;10;5)} \rightarrow \underline{(-3;2;7;3)} + \underline{(-1;0;0;0)}$$

Anti-Strange-Quark-Decay

$$\underline{\mathbf{s}}^{+0.33} \rightarrow W^+ + \underline{\mathbf{u}}^{-0.67} \rightarrow \underline{\mathbf{u}}^{-0.6} + \pi^+(\underline{\mathbf{u}}, \mathbf{d}) \quad (28)$$

from $K^+(\underline{\mathbf{s}}, \mathbf{u})$

from $\pi^0(\underline{\mathbf{u}}, \underline{\mathbf{u}})$

Rishon:

($\mathbf{u}$) + ($\mathbf{d}$)

$$[2\underline{\text{TT}} + \underline{\text{VV}} + \underline{\text{VVT}}^{+0.3}] \rightarrow \underline{(\text{TT})\text{TVV}(\text{V})^+} + \underline{\text{TTV}}^{-0.67} \rightarrow \underline{\text{TTV}}^{+0.66} + \underline{\text{VVT}}^{+0.33} + \underline{\text{TTV}}^{-0.66}$$

Interactions:

$$(3;2;5;17) \rightarrow (0;0;10;5) + \underline{(1;2;4;8)} \rightarrow (1;2;4;8) + (2;2;4;8) + \underline{(1;2;4;8)}$$

Thereby the Rishon-content of the strange-quark and myon are written according to Elbaz [23,24].

According to the Elbaz-notation [24], which is slightly modified here, of the elementary particles the intra-particle interactions are as follows:

Electron: $a=-1[\underline{\text{TTT}}(\underline{\text{VV}})]$ Myon: $a=-3[\underline{\text{TTT}}(\underline{\text{VV}})_3]$ strange-Quark: $a=3[\underline{\text{VVT}}(\underline{\text{TT}})_2(\underline{\text{VV}})]$

$$a=4-1=3$$

[V V ... I (-1,2,4,4) [V V ... I (-3.2.7.3) [V V ... V (3,2,5,17)

I

V V ... I

I T ... I

I]

V V ... I]

V ... T I]

1 binding

3 binding

4 non-binding, 1 binding

It can be recognized that a binding 2-particle interaction ($a < 0$) occurs between an antimatter T and a matter V, and/or a matter T and an anti-matter V. It seems that **both need to change** T to V and matter to antimatter in order to form a binding interaction.

On the other hand a matter V- to antimatter V interaction and/or an matter T- to antimatter T interaction as in the strange quark is non-binding ($a > 0$). Also a T to V and or anti-T to anti-V binding as in the u-quark, d-quark, and s-quark are non-binding. Homomorphic bindings as TT, TT and/or VV and/or VV bindings in the particles do not count.

u-quark $a=1[\underline{\text{TTV}}]$

u-quark $a=1[\underline{\text{TTV}}]$

d-quark $a=2[\underline{\text{VTV}}]$

[T (1,2,4,8)

[T (1,2,4,8)

[V (2,2,4,8)

T

I

I

V]

V]

V]

1 non-binding

1 non-binding

2 non-binding

Tauon: $a=1[\underline{\text{TTT}}(\underline{\text{VV}})_6]$

W^+ -particle $a=0[\underline{\text{TTT}}(\underline{\text{VVV}})]$

Z-particle: $a=0[\underline{\text{VVV}}(\underline{\text{VVV}})]$

[----- V V ... I (1,2,7,7)

[V ... T (0,0,10,5)

[V ... V (0,0,10,14)

V V ... I

V ... T

V ... V

V V ... I

V ... T]

V ... V]

(V V)₃-----

1 non-binding

zero binding

zero binding

$$v_{\tau}=[VVV(VV)_3]$$

$$W^- \text{-particle } a=0 \text{ [TTT(VVV)] } (0,0,10,5)$$

$$v_e=[VVV]$$

Forming the W-particle: Through adding of TTV to d the a and b- interactions get somewhat lost. Only the c and d interaction are possible in the W-particle. Afterwards the W-particle forms two particles with a and b interactions again.

Modifications of the Elbaz notations were made in order to meet the particle decays.

Decay of the Tauon:

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \tau^- \quad \rightarrow \quad W^- \quad + \quad \nu_{\tau} \quad \rightarrow \quad \mu^- \text{ (or } e^- \text{ or } d^{-0.3}) + \quad \underline{\nu}_{\mu} \text{ (or } \underline{\nu}_{e,u}) \\
 [\text{-----} \underline{V} \text{ V} \dots \underline{I} \quad \quad \quad [\underline{V} \dots \underline{I} \quad \quad \quad [\underline{VV} \dots \underline{I} \\
 \underline{V} \text{ V} \dots \underline{I} \quad \rightarrow \quad \underline{V} \dots \underline{I} \quad + \quad VVV(\underline{VV})_3 \quad \quad \quad \underline{VV} \dots \underline{I} \quad + \quad \underline{VVV} \\
 \underline{V} \text{ V} \dots \underline{I} \quad \quad \quad \underline{V} \dots \underline{I} \quad \quad \quad \underline{VV} \dots \underline{I}] \\
 (V \underline{V})_3 \text{-----}] \\
 \underline{(1,2,7,7)} \quad \rightarrow \quad \underline{(0,0,10,5)} + \quad (-1,-2,0,0) \rightarrow \quad \underline{(-3,2,7,3)} + \quad \underline{(-1,0,0,0)}
 \end{array}$$

1 non-binding

The proportionality factor between the value of the microcanonical partition function and the rest energy (equivalent to the rest mass) of the particle, the following values are obtained for the nucleon, the electron and the sigma baryon:

for the proton:

$$f_p = E_{0,p} / Z_{m,p} = \frac{E_{0,p}}{\Omega_p} = 938.272 \cdot 10^6 eV / 6.8953127 \cdot 10^7 = 13.6074137 eV \quad (29)$$

for the electron:

$$f_e = E_{0,e} / Z_e = \frac{E_{0,e}}{\Omega_e} = 0.51099895 MeV / 37553 = 13.6074068 eV \quad (30)$$

for the sigma baryon:

$$f_{Sigma} = E_{0,\Sigma} / Z_{\Sigma} = \frac{E_{0,\Sigma}}{\Omega_{\Sigma}} = 1192.642 \cdot 10^6 \text{ eV} / 8.7648980 \cdot 10^7 = 13.60702657 \text{ eV} \quad (31)$$

Rydberg proportionality factor

This factor, equally to the microcanonical density operator is almost identical to the Rydberg energy ($E_{\text{Ryd}}=13.605693122 \text{ eV}$). At first glance, this result seems astonishing. If we assume, however, that the Rydberg energy does not merely represent the binding energy of the electron to the proton but rather should be considered to be the smallest energy quantum for all quantum mechanical binding then the problem is solved. This smallest amount of binding represents binding in general and the binding energy in every particle. Or more general the smallest amount of energy which can be absorbed in a quantum mechanical setting on the elementary particle level. Additionally, it gets clear that the more interactions are present in a particle and the more binding-quanta are therefore needed and present in the particle, the more binding energy must consequently result and be present in the respective particle. This binding energy now seems to exist in a quantized form only, and the smallest quantum of this binding-energy seems to be identical to the Rydberg energy. Hence, the Rydberg energy is not only the ionization energy of the hydrogen atom but has a much more general meaning and importance.

On the other hand Rydbergs energy equals to the energy density operator of this microcanonical ensemble.

If we consider the zero-tupel (0,0,0,0) then this zero-tupel has a value of 1 Rydberg. So for a binding mediated through one gluon, and with zero vertices involved, too, we still have a binding energy of 1 Rydberg. This also equals to the energy of one standard gluon and/or to the energy of one Feynman diagram.

The Rydberg energy seems to be the amount of energy of one microstate of the statistical ensemble that is formed by the binding states within a particle. The partition function Z given here yields the number of microstates realized in one respective particle, which can be visualized as an ensemble of Feynman-like structures describing this particular particle.

However the neutrino might have negative exponents. This would allow smaller binding energies than Rydberg's energy. As the experimental results suggest a mass for the neutrino smaller than $<1 \text{ eV}/c^2$.

We draw the following conclusions, which are valid for particles only:

$$m \sim E \sim Z \sim \Omega \sim N_{\text{microstates}} \quad \text{or} \quad m \sim E \sim \Omega \quad (32a+32b)$$

$$\rho = \frac{E}{Z} = E_{\text{Rydberg}} \quad \text{or} \quad \rho = \frac{E}{\Omega} = E_{\text{Rydberg}} \quad (33a+33b)$$

$$E = E_{\text{Rydberg}} \cdot Z \quad \text{or} \quad E = E_{\text{Rydberg}} \cdot \Omega \quad (34a+34b)$$

Generalization of the partition function and generalization of the energy (mass) relation

A generalization of the partition function results in the following general formulation of the microcanonical partition function of a particle.

The mass of an elementary particle can also be expressed in general using the following relationship.

$$E_{\text{particle}} = m_{\text{particle}} c^2 = 2^a \cdot 3^b \cdot (3\pi)^c \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[8]{1 - \frac{1}{3\pi}}} \right)^d \cdot E_{\text{Ryd}} \quad (35) \text{ similar to (6)}$$

Here, the exponents a, b, c, and d are related to the numbers of interactions present in the respective particle.

This formulation yields the following hypotheses:

1.) The constant of proportionality between the partition function of a particle and the energy (mass) of that particle is always the Rydberg energy (the energy per microstate and/or energy density).

$$Z_m = \Omega = 2^a \cdot 3^b \cdot (3\pi)^c \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[8]{1 - \frac{1}{3\pi}}} \right)^d \quad (36)$$

$$E = 2^a \cdot 3^b \cdot (3\pi)^c \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[8]{1 - \frac{1}{3\pi}}} \right)^d \cdot E_{Ryd} \quad (37)$$

2.) The individual exponents a, b, c, and d are always small whole numbers representing numbers of interactions. Z describes the number of possible combinations of such individual interactions. For all known particles, these exponents (a,b,c,d) can be determined through trial and error. Doing so leads us to the exponent series given in table 1. These values result from comparing the masses for well-known particles resulting from the formula given above with the experimentally known values from the Particle Data Group. Another approach for determining the number of possible combinations consists of the graphic representation of all conceivable combination possibilities, analogous to what has been demonstrated here for the proton or nucleon and the pion.

3.) When we take a closer look at the values in table 1, we see that there are some particles that have no quark–quark and/or no rishon-rishon interactions at all. These particles seem to exist due to gluons only; examples include the W, Z and H particles. Because these particles are bosons and are known to transmit forces, this finding is well consistent with current knowledge about particles.

4.) The fact, that experimental determined energy states of excited sigma-baryons can be described with a qq-model is in line with the description used here (quark-diquark model). The quark-diquark model was developed by Lichtenberg et al 1968 [25] and has successfully been used for the description of the hadron spectroscopy (Nagata et al, [26]). The model for the sigma-baryon described here is very similar to the quark –diquark model and can potentially be an explanation for why this model is working very well. The exponential series for the delta-resonances (uud, ddu) are (-3;2;8;18). Similarly to the sigma baryon also the delta resonances have an a of -3. Therefore this could be an explanation for the quark di-quark model of Lichtenberg also fitting very good for the delta and nucleon resonances.

Comparison with textbook knowledge

In textbooks [17], a proportional relation between energies and/or between the potency of energy and the microcanonical partition function is described for the microcanonical ensemble only. This relation is completely different than that for a canonical or macrocanonical ensemble. For those two types of ensembles, a logarithmic relationship between the energy and the partition function has been described. Here we are dealing with a microcanonical statistical ensemble and the resulting partition function. It could be expected that a linear relationship would exist between the appropriate partition function and the binding energy.

Considerations on the Accuracy of the Calculations presented here

To compare the accuracy of the calculations presented here with that of the previously available formulas, we determine the electron mass or rest energy in two ways.

On the one hand, we calculate the electron rest energy using the new method presented here, and on the other hand, we use the well-known (and similar) relationship between the Rydberg constant and the electron mass ($Ry=13.605693122$ eV).

$$E_{e,0} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot 3^2 \cdot (3\pi)^4 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt[8]{1 - \frac{1}{3\pi}}} \right)^4 \cdot E_{Ryd} = 37554 \text{ Ry} \quad (38)$$

By comparing the results of both methods of determining the electron mass, we can see that with the new method, we determine the rest energy of the electron, measured in Rydbergs as the energy unit, to be 37554 Ry (nominal experimental value: 37557 Ry); this value is accurate to four decimal places ($1 E_{Ryd}=13.605693122$ eV, $m_{Ryd}=13.605693122\text{eV}/c^2$).

$$m_e = E_{Ryd} \frac{\varepsilon^2 h^2 8}{e^4} = 9.11282233567 \cdot 10^{-31} \text{ kg} \quad (39)$$

Using the analogous previously well-known common relationship (equation 39), we determine the electron mass to be $9.112822335674\text{E}-31$ kg (nominal experimental value $9.109 \text{ E}-31$ kg), corresponding to an accuracy of only two decimal places. The novel relation between the Rydberg constant and the experimental electron mass presented here is therefore far more precise than the previously known relationship (equation 39), with an accuracy that is higher by two decimal places (a factor of approximately 100 more accurate or two more decimal places).

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Figure Legends

Figure 1

With the information given in this manuscript, we can formulate “binding-pictures” for the elementary particles similar to the formulas and pictures used for the molecules in chemistry today.

There are different kinds of interactions within a nucleon. These are the color – anticolor interactions, which are 2-particle interactions, the normal color interactions which are three-particle interactions, the 3-gluon vertices, and the 4-gluon vertices. All these interactions can also be graphically displayed analogously to the chemical bonding in molecules. Here this is done exemplarily for the nucleon.

- a.) Graphical representation of the number of color–anticolor interactions (a) for the nucleon
- b.) Graphical representation of the number of three-color interactions (b) for the nucleon
- c.) Graphical representation of the number of 3-gluon vertex interactions (c) for the nucleon
- d.) Graphical representation of the number of 4-gluon vertex interactions (d) for the nucleon. Thereby 3-gluon vertex interactions and 4-gluon vertex interactions are combined.

Figure 2

There are different kinds of interactions within a neutral pion. These are the color – anticolor interactions, which are 2-particle interactions, the normal color-interactions which are normally three-particle interactions, the 3-gluon vertices, and the 4-gluon interactions. Again, all these interactions can be displayed graphically analogously to the chemical binding in molecules. Here this is done for the neutral pion, which turned out to be a pion-pion dimer.

- a.) Graphical representation of the number of color–anticolor interactions (a) for the neutral pion. The neutral pion is considered to be a quantum-mechanical state of superposition. This superposition is considered to form a pion-dimer meaning that both pions involved enter into interactions.
- b.) Graphical representation of the number of three-color interactions (b) for the pion-dimer
- c.) Graphical representation of the number of 3-vertex gluon interactions (c) for the pion-dimer
- d.) Graphical representation of the number of 4-vertex gluon interactions (d) for the pion-dimer. Again 3-gluon vertex interactions and 4-gluon vertex interactions are combined.

Since the pion is considered to be a superposition and/or dimer the numbers a,b,c,d need to be divided by two.

Figure 3

Again, there are different kinds of interactions within a sigma baryon. These are the color – anticolor interactions, which are 2-particle interactions, the normal color interactions which normally are three-particle interactions, the 3-gluon vertices, and the 4-gluon interactions. Again, all these interactions can be displayed graphically analogously to the chemical bindings in molecules. Here this is done for the sigma baryon. The sigma baryon carries the strange quark and the strange quark has the ability to take part in two particle interactions (=color anticolor interactions).

a.) Graphical representation of the number of color–anticolor interactions (a) for the sigma baryon

The strange-quark seems to have the ability to interact in anticolor interactions. So it seems to have the ability to carry anticolor.

b.) Graphical representation of the number of three-color interactions (b) for the sigma baryon

c.) Graphical representation of the number of 3-vertex gluon interactions (c) for the sigma baryon

d.) Graphical representation of the number of 4-vertex gluon interactions (d) for the sigma baryon

Again 3-gluon vertex interactions and 4-gluon vertex interactions are combined. Two 4-gluon interactions seem to occur subsequently in the sigma baryon.

Tables

Table 1

This table gives the exponents series (a,b,c,d) for the most important particles using the mathematical pi.

Table 2

This table gives the exponents series (a,b,c,d) for the most important particles using the physical pi and the reduced physical pi. Thereby the physical pi is the pi which is derived through the coupling constant linked to pi. And the reduced pi is a pi with a reduced amount of decimals (3.14). The rationale for using the reduced physical pi is that Planck's length might lie in a similar order of magnitude than pi leading to a reduced number of decimal positions in pi.

Figure 1 Protons duu and Neutrons udd ($a=0; b=-2; c=9; d=4$)
 Quantum State Sum Ensembles for the Parameters a and b
 in the protons and/or neutrons we have the following interactions:

a.)

no color- anticolor interaction
 $a=0$

b.)

three color interaction rgb
 one three anticolor interaction
 $b=-2$
 both are binding

Figure 1 Protons and Neutrons ($a=0; b=-2; c=9; d=4$)
 Quantum State Sum Ensembles for the Parameters c and d
 3-gluon vertices (c) and 4-gluon vertices (d)

Figure 2 neutral Pions $u\bar{u}+d\bar{d}$ ($a=-1$; $b=1$; $c=7$; $d=0$)
 Quantum State Sum Ensembles for the Parameters a and b
 formulated as pion-dimers analog to the wave function

Figure 2 neutral Pions ($a=-1; b=1; c=7; d=0$) State Sum, Parameters c and d

c.)

d.)

$c=8, d=4$

$a=-2:2=-1$ per mono
 $b=2:2=1$ per mono
 $c=14:2 = 7$ per mono
 $d=4:2=2$ per mono

Figure 3 neutral Sigma-baryon uds ($a=-3$; $b=2$; $c=8$; $d=16$) Parameters a and b

a.) three color-anticolor interactions

b.)

Figure 3 neutral Sigma-bar-von ($a=-3; b=2; c=8; d=16$) Parameters c and d

Table 1 Exponent- series of the mass- formula calculated for the different particles with the mathematical pi

a	b	c	d	mass/[MeV]	particle	composition
leptons						
-1	-2	0	0	7E-7	neutrino	(VV)V
-1	2	4	4	0.5109	electron	(TT)T
-3	2	7	3	105.44	muon	TTT*
1	2	7	7	1784.49	tauon	TTT**
quarks						
1	2	4	8	2.16	up	u,(tt)v;vtv;ttv
2	2	4	8	4.67	down	d, (VV)T;VTV;TVV
2	3	6	15	1270	charm	c ttv*
3	2	5	17	92	strange	s TVV*
1	2	9	13	172421	top	t ttv**
2	3	6	100	4184	bottom	b TVV**
vector bosons						
0	0	10	5	80700.0	W	(TT)T(VV)V
0	0	10	14	91554.0	Z	
0	0	10	36	124634.0	H	
mesons						
-1	1	7	0	134.8	pi 0	(uu-dd)/2
-1	0	8	11	494.128	K+	us
-1	-2	9	15	547.299	eta 0	uu+dd-2ss
0	0	8	9	960.9	eta dash	uu+dd+ss
1	0	8	7	1868.71	D+	cd
1	0	8	11	1976.5	Ds+	cs
-1	0	9	20	5283.0	B meson	ub
-1	0	9	22	5433.0	strange meson	sb
-1	0	9	33	6339.0	charm meson	cb
vector mesons						
3	0	7	5	771.0	rho 0	(uu-dd)/2
0	0	8	4	895.872	K*0	ds
3	0	7	6	782.0	omega	(uu+dd)/2
0	0	8	13	1016	phi	ss
1	0	8	12	2004.0	D*0	cu
1	0	8	43	3095.6	J/psi	cc
baryons						
0	-2	9	4	938.15	proton	uud
-3	2	8	11	1111.0	lambda	uds
-3	2	8	16	1192.5	sigma 0	uds
-3	2	8	18	1226.4	delta	ddd
-3	2	8	23	1315.5	xi 0	uss
-1	-1	9	3	1387.6	sigma-*	dds
-3	2	8	29	1430.95	N(1440)	udd
-1	-1	9	10	1530.7	xi 0 reson	uss

1	0	8	1	1670.0	Omega -	sss
-3	2	8	63	2304.0	lambda-c	udc
-3	2	8	68	2472.0	c-sigma	ddc
			129	5815.0	cascade B	usb
-3	2	8	130	5897.0	bottom sigma	ddb
-3	2	8	72	2614.9	charmed xi prime	usc
-3	2	8	96	3661.0	double charmed xi	ucc

Table 2 Exponent- series of the mass- formula calculated for the different particles using the physical pi as derived by Sommerfelds alpha (3.141677) and the reduced physical pi (3.14)

a	b	c	d	mass	particle	composition
leptons						
-1	2	4	4	0.510999	electron	TTT
-3	2	7	3	105.468	muon	TTT*
1	2	7	7	1778.26	tauon	TTT** with 3.14
quarks						
1	2	4	8	2.1618	up	u, TTV, TVT, VTT
2	2	4	8	4.323	down	d, TVV, VTV, VVT
2	3	6	15	1271	charm	c
3	2	5	17	92.46	strange	s
1	2	9	13	172462	top	t
2	3	6	100	4185	bottom	b
vector bosons						
0	0	10	5	80295.0	W	3.14
0	0	10	14	91100.4	Z	3.14
0	0	10	36	124666.0	H	
mesons						
-1	1	7	0	134.8314	pi 0	(uu-dd)/2
-1	0	8	11	494.232	K+	us
-1	-2	9	15	547.428	eta 0	uu+dd-2ss
0	0	8	9	961.132	eta dash	uu+dd+ss
1	0	8	7	1869.11	D+	cd
1	0	8	11	1968.67	Ds+	Cs with 3.14
-1	0	9	20	5284.62	B meson	ub
-1	0	9	22	5434.90	strange meson	sb
-1	0	9	33	6341.17	charm meson	cb
vector mesons						
3	0	7	5	768.5	rho 0	(uu-dd)/2 w3.14
0	0	8	4	892	K*0	Ds with 3.14
3	0	7	6	782.21	omega	(uu+dd)/2
0	0	8	13	1016.57	phi	ss
1	0	8	12	2004.84	D*0	cu
1	0	8	43	3096.25	J/psi	cc
baryons						
0	-2	9	4	938.3	proton	uud
-3	2	8	11	1112.02	lambda	uds
-3	2	8	16	1192.77	sigma 0	uds
-3	2	8	18	1226.69	delta	ddd
-3	2	8	23	1315.77	xi 0	uss
-1	-1	9	3	1387.97	sigma-*	dds
-3	2	8	29	1431.24	N(1440)	udd
-1	-1	9	10	1531.1	xi 0 reson	uss
1	0	8	1	1718.31	Omega -	sss

-3	2	8	63	2305.35	lambda-c	udc
-3	2	8	68	2472.76	c-sigma	ddc
-3	-2	8	129	5815.74	cascade B	usb
-3	2	8	130	5897.85	bottom sigma	ddb
-3	2	8	72	2615.39	charmed xi prime	usc
-3	2	8	96	3661.598	double charmed xi	ucc